

A Kinetic Study of Acid-catalysed Oxidation of *N*-Methyl-2,6-diphenyl-4-piperidones by Thallium(III) Acetate

(MRS) KR MEENAL* and (MRS.) S. LALITHA

Department of Chemistry, Seethalakshmi Ramaswami College (Autonomous), Trichy-620 002

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Kinetics of oxidation of 1-methyl-, 1-methyl-3-alkyl- and 1,3,5-trimethyl-2,6-diphenyl-4-piperidones by thallium(III) acetate have been investigated at different temperatures (40–60°) in aqueous acetic acid (80%, v/v) and sulphuric acid (0.75 mol dm⁻³). Oxidation is found to obey second order kinetics which conforms to that reported for Tl^{III} oxidation of *N*-H-4-piperidones in our earlier study. Activation parameters were calculated to substantiate the mechanism. Primary salt-effect was examined using sodium sulphate. The reaction rate increases with the increase in percentage of acetic acid. The possible mechanism of the reaction has been discussed on the basis of stoichiometry and product isolated.

The oxidation of 4-piperidones has been studied in considerable detail with potassium permanganate¹, vanadium(v)^{2,3}, chromium(vi)⁴ and cerium(iv)⁵. Our earlier work on Tl^{III} oxidation of *N*-H-4-piperidones prompted us to undertake the title investigation to study the effect of introducing CH₃ group in the heteroatom-N. Tl^{III} is essentially a two-electron oxidant and hence attacks the enol form of the ketone⁶ forming oxythallation adduct⁷ in the rate-controlling step.

Results and Discussion

Oxidation of a series of *N*-methyl-4-piperidones by Tl^{III} was carried out in aqueous acetic acid at constant acidity. The reaction was practically negligible in the absence of added mineral acid and was conveniently carried out by maintaining required concentration of H₂SO₄ (0.75 mol dm⁻³). The constant values of pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{obs}) were evaluated by the method of least-squares at different initial [Tl^{III}]. At constant [H⁺], the kinetics agreed with the rate law,

$$\frac{-d[\text{Tl}^{\text{III}}]}{dt} = k[\text{Tl}^{\text{III}}][\text{substrate}]$$

The reaction rate increased with an increase in

[H₂SO₄] (Table 1) and the change of ionic strength had negligible effect on the reaction rate. The order with respect to [H⁺] from the slope of the plots of log k_2 vs log [H⁺], was found to vary with the substrate : 1.0, 0.7, 0.5, 0.8, 0.7 and 0.6 for 3-isopropyl, 3-H, 3-methyl, 3-ethyl, 3,3-dimethyl and 3,5-dimethyl respectively. The corresponding correlation coefficients of linear plots were found to be 0.92, 0.99, 0.99, 0.99, 0.97 and 0.99. The order less than unity found may be due to the reversibility of the hydrolysis of the oxythallation adduct.

Study of the reaction using HOAc-H₂O mixture of different proportions shows (Table 2) that there is increase in the rate with increase in acetic acid content of the solvent. This may be attributed to a lowering of dielectric constant of the medium which favours ion-dipole type of reactions. The activation parameters evaluated from the Arrhenius plots are given in Table 3. The nearly same free energy of activation of the order of 90 KJ mol⁻¹ suggests a similar type of mechanism to be operative in the oxidation of all the piperidones studied.

The reaction system did not induce polymerisation of added acrylonitrile confirming that there are no free radicals in the system.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF VARYING [PIPERIDONE], [Ti^{III}] AND [H₂SO₄] ON THE RATES OF OXIDATIONS

Concn. mol dm ⁻³	3-Isopropyl	3-H	3-Methyl	3-Ethyl	3,3-Dimethyl	3,5-Dimethyl
	318 K	318 K	318 K	323 K	328 K	328 K
	<i>k</i> _{obs} (× 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹)					
[Piperidone] × 10 ²						
1.5	2.09	1.47	1.11	2.14	1.42	0.21
2.0	2.81	1.85	1.44	2.81	1.88	0.28
2.5	3.51	2.42	1.86	3.48	2.36	0.36
3.0	4.20	2.88	2.16	4.14	2.84	0.42
Ti ^{III} × 10 ³						
1.5	2.75	1.84	1.42	2.58	1.98	0.28
2.0	2.81	1.85	1.44	2.40	1.88	0.28
2.5	2.62	1.79	1.41	2.45	1.93	0.27
3.0	2.67	1.80	1.33	2.63	1.98	0.26
[H ₂ SO ₄]						
0.5	1.32	1.48	1.23	1.96	1.26	0.24
0.75	2.81	1.85	1.44	2.48	1.88	0.28
1.0	3.12	2.28	1.65	3.37	2.04	0.36
1.25	3.40	2.69	1.95	4.21	2.32	0.40

TABLE 2—EFFECTS OF VARYING SOLVENT COMPOSITION

[Ti^{III}] = 2 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [Piperidone] = 2 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³, [H₂SO₄] = 0.75 mol dm⁻³

Piperidone	% HOAc (v/v)			
	75	80	85	90
	<i>k</i> _{obs} (× 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹)			
3-Isopropyl (318 K)	1.84	2.81	3.67	5.12
3-H (318 K)	1.38	1.85	2.83	3.14
3-Methyl (318 K)	1.14	1.44	2.71	2.94
3-Ethyl (323 K)	1.86	2.81	3.92	7.25
3,3-Dimethyl (328 K)	1.32	1.88	3.21	5.97
3,5-Dimethyl (328 K)	0.19	0.28	0.34	0.42

TABLE 3—RATE CONSTANTS AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS AT 318 K

Piperidone	× 10 ³ <i>k</i> ₂ mol ⁻¹ dm ³ s ⁻¹	<i>E</i> _a KJ mol ⁻¹	Δ <i>H</i> [‡] KJ mol ⁻¹	Δ <i>G</i> [‡] KJ mol ⁻¹	Δ <i>S</i> [‡] JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
3-Isopropyl	14.0	68.5	65.9	89.3	-73.6
3-H	9.27	93.2	90.6	90.4	0.6
3-Methyl	7.21	101.0	98.6	91.1	23.6
3-Ethyl	7.79	102.0	99.8	90.9	28.0
3,3-Dimethyl	2.72	108.0	106.0	93.7	38.1
3,5-Dimethyl	0.61	69.3	66.7	97.6	-97.2

Structure-reactivity relationship : A perusal of data (Table 1) shows that the order of reactivity among piperidones is 3-isopropyl > 3-H > 3-methyl ≈ 3-ethyl > 3,3-dimethyl > 3,5-dimethyl. With the exception of 3-isopropyl, the order of reactivity is in consonance with the stability of the oxythallation adduct. The lowering of reactivity by 3-alkyl substituent can be attributed to steric factor. The higher

reactivity of *N*-methyl-2,6-diphenylpiperidone is due to the strainless chair form and the availability of α-H on either side of the carbonyl group. It is of interest to note that the H-attached to nitrogen in piperidone is axial⁸. Whereas in *N*-methylpiperidones the methyl group prefers the most stable equatorial position⁹ leaving the lone-pair of electrons at the axial position. Besides, methyl group incidentally increases the electron density around nitrogen atom thereby distracting the electrophilic attack by Ti(OAc)₂⁺ on the π-electron cloud. This may be responsible for the considerable reduction in the rate of oxidation of *N*-methyl series compared to *N*-H-series (our earlier work). The anomalous behaviour of 3-isopropyl, highly reactive piperidone of the present series, may be attributed to steric enhancement which needs further evidential clarification. In the case of 1,3,5-trimethyl, the presence of methyl groups on either side of the carbonyl group (twist chair form) not only strongly hinders the attack of oxidant but also limits the oxidation to the first stage of the product (acyloin).

Mechanism and rate law : Ti(OAc)₃ in aqueous acetic acid has been found to be unreactive presumably because of the complexing of thallic ion by acetate ion. However, we have found that addition of strong acid (H₂SO₄) accelerates the oxidation, no doubt by proton removal of acetate groups from the coordination sphere of the thallic ion to give a thallic species of higher reactivity¹⁰,

The calculated values of stability constants assuming the maximum n is 4 by the method of Rossotti and Rossotti¹¹ at various acetate ion concentrations are $K_4 = 2.09 \times 10^2$ and $K_3 = 3.62 \times 10^3$ (Ref. 7). The higher stability constant value of K_3 favours the second step. Hence the active oxidising species of Ti^{III} under our experimental condition is Ti(OAc)_2^+ (eqn. 1). In the medium of 80% (v/v) aqueous acetic acid and 0.75 mol dm^{-3} sulphuric acid, piperidone exists in the enol form and Ti^{III} being a two-electron oxidant attacks the enol form⁶ giving oxythallation adduct (eqn. 2) in the slow rate-limiting step which on subsequent hydrolysis yields the α -hydroxy ketone (eqn. 3) which undergoes further oxidation utilising one more mole of the oxidant giving the product isolated α -diketone (eqn. 4). In the case of 1,3,5-trimethyl the oxidation is limited to the formation of the α -hydroxyketone. To account for the foregoing experimental observations the mechanism presented in Scheme 1 may be envisaged in accordance with the rate law,

$$\frac{d[\text{Ti}^{\text{III}}]}{dt} = k_1 k_2 [\text{piperidone}] [\text{Ti(OAc)}_3]$$

Experimental

Thallic oxide (B.D.H.) was dissolved in hot acetic acid (Qualigen, A.R., unaffected by CrO_3), filtered and the solution standardised iodometrically. Conductivity water was used for preparing the solvent mixtures. All other chemicals used were of reagent grade. The *N*-methyl-2,6-diphenylpiperidones were prepared by the reported procedure¹². The reaction was initiated adding the required amount of oxidant to the piperidone solution in 80% $\text{HOAc-H}_2\text{O}$ mixture equilibrated at constant acidity. The reaction was followed by estimating the unconsumed Ti^{III}

at regular intervals of time iodometrically. For all the kinetic runs the substrate concentration was kept ten-fold excess over that of the oxidant and pseudo-first order principle was followed to get the rate constants (k_{obs}) for about 50% of the reaction. The duplicate rate measurements were reproducible to $\pm 3\%$.

Stoichiometric investigation showed the consumption of two moles of oxidant by one mole of *N*-methyl-3-alkylpiperidone and one mole of oxidant by one mole of 1,3,5-trimethylpiperidone. The reaction mixture was neutralised with NH_3 , extracted with ether and the ether extract evaporated. The oily liquid obtained was tested for the presence of 1,2-diketone by treating with hydroxylamine hydrochloride, alkali and Ni^{II} . The diketone was characterised by the development of red colour. In the case of 1,3,5-trimethylpiperidone, the oxidation was limited to the formation of α -hydroxyketone as per the stoichiometry. The products were further characterised by tlc, ir and nmr. The product from 1,3-dimethylpiperidone gave ν_{max} at 1700 cm^{-1} (C=O) and ^1H nmr signals at δ 0.85 (3H, d, 3-Me) 1.80 (3H, s, N-Me), 3.00 (1H, m, 3-H), 3.80 (1H, d, 6-H) 4.00 (1H, d, 6-H) and 7.3–7.7 (10H, m, 2 and 6-Ph). The product from 1,3,5-trimethyl-

piperidone gave ν_{\max} at 2 900–3 100 cm^{-1} (C-OH) and ^1H nmr signals at δ 0.85 (3H, d, 3-Me), 1.50 (3H, s, 5-Me), 1.80 (3H, s, N-Me), 3.00 (1H, m, 3-H), 3.80 (2H, m, 2 and 6-H), 7.3–7.7 (10H, m, 2- and 6-Ph) and 9.5 (1H, s, OH).

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